

1 **Quantifying the coupling effects of tectonics, climate, and**
2 **lithology on the main drainage divide of a mountain belt**

3 Chao Zhou^{1,2}, Xibin Tan^{3*}, Yongzhong Yang³, Feng Shi^{1,2}, Yiduo Liu³

4 ¹ State Key Laboratory of Earthquake Dynamics, Institute of Geology, China

5 Earthquake Administration, Beijing, 100029, China

6 ² Shanxi Taiyuan Continental Rift Dynamics National Observation and Research

7 Station, Institute of Geology, China Earthquake Administration, Beijing, 100029,

8 China

9 ³ Key Laboratory of Mountain Hazards and Engineering Resilience, Institute of

10 Mountain Hazards and Environment, Chinese Academy of Sciences, Chengdu

11 610213, China

12 *Corresponding author: tanxibin@imde.ac.cn

13

14 **Abstract**

15 The formation and evolution of the main drainage divide (MDD) of mountain
16 belts are of great significance in Earth's system as they control water allocation and
17 species exchange. Extensive research has focused on deciphering the controlling
18 factors (including vertical and horizontal tectonic movements, climate, and lithology)
19 of MDD morphologies. However, a persistent limitation is the predominant focus on
20 analyzing these controlling factors in isolation or in parts. Here, we develop a
21 comprehensive equation for the steady-state position of MDD, which integrates all the
22 tectonic and non-tectonic factors examined in previous work. We further conduct
23 numerical simulations to verify the robustness of this equation. Additionally, based on
24 the equation, we design an interactive program that allows users to predict an MDD's
25 stable position under the set parameters. We also apply the equation to two natural
26 examples to demonstrate its utility. This study will facilitate not only a deeper
27 understanding of the evolution mechanism of the Earth's surface but also the
28 reconstruction of tectonic and/or climatic processes from mountain belt morphology.

29 **Keywords:**

30 Drainage divide; Constraint equation; Numerical simulation; Eastern Tibet; Shanxi
31 continental rift

32

33 **1. Introduction**

34 Mountain belts represent one of the core research themes in geosciences.
35 Tectonic and climatic forces together shape the mountains (Davis et al., 1983; Platt,
36 1986; Willett et al., 1993; Anders et al., 1993; Goren et al., 2014); in turn, the
37 landscape of mountain belts is frequently used to reconstruct tectonic and climatic
38 processes (Willett, 1999; Miller et al., 2007; He et al., 2021; Zhou et al., 2022a). The
39 main drainage divide (MDD) is one of the most conspicuous features of a mountain
40 belt and holds rich tectonic and climatic information. Active mountain belts
41 experience both vertical and horizontal tectonic movements (Fig. 1). Meanwhile,
42 spatial heterogeneities in lithology and precipitation exist in mountain belts (Willett
43 and Brandon, 2002; Forte et al., 2014). Quantifying the coupling effects of tectonics
44 (including vertical and horizontal movements), climate, and lithology on MDD,
45 therefore, is a prerequisite for quantitatively extracting tectonic or climatic
46 information. Moreover, as the MDD controls water allocation and species exchange
47 (He et al., 2024; Liu et al., 2024), understanding its response to tectonic activity
48 and/or climate change remains a key issue in Earth system science.

49 Many studies have examined the factors controlling MDD morphologies in
50 mountain belts. Early studies used numerical simulations to explore parameters'
51 impact (Willett et al., 2001; Willett and Brandon, 2002). Subsequently, analytical
52 solutions for MDD positions were formulated (Miller and Slingerland, 2006; Miller et
53 al., 2007; Goren et al., 2014). Building on these advancements, constraint equations
54 for MDD positions have been developed and refined, with additional controlling

55 factors incorporated to enhance their applicability (He et al., 2021; Shi et al., 2021;
56 Zhou et al., 2022a). However, a persistent limitation is that most studies analyze the
57 tectonic, climatic, and lithological factors in isolation or in parts. For instance, when
58 quantifying tectonic uplift's effect on MDD, horizontal movement is assumed absent;
59 when analyzing horizontal movement's impact, uplift, climate, and lithology are
60 assumed uniform (He et al., 2021; Shi et al., 2021; Zhou et al., 2022a). This gap
61 restricts the generalizability of tectonic and/or climatic information extraction from
62 topography in natural cases. Therefore, quantifying their combined effects on the
63 MDD remains an outstanding issue.

64 In this study, we present a comprehensive constraint equation for the steady-state
65 MDD position in active mountain belts. It incorporates tectonic (vertical and
66 horizontal movements) and non-tectonic factors (lithology, precipitation, base level
67 elevation, drainage basin geometry). We validate this equation through numerical
68 simulations under a broad range of geological conditions. Besides, to enhance the
69 practical utility of the theoretical framework, we develop an interactive program for
70 users to predict the steady-state positions of MDD based on input. Furthermore,
71 applying the equation to two natural examples, Wutai Shan and Min Shan,
72 demonstrate its utility. Collectively, this approach enables geological information
73 extraction from mountain belt morphology under generalized conditions and provides
74 new opportunities for deciphering interactions between tectonics and surface
75 processes in mountain belts.

76

2. The equation for the steady-state position of MDD

We build a simplified geometric model for tectonic-geomorphic processes in mountain belts (Fig. 1), based on previous studies (Willett et al., 2001; Willett and Brandon, 2002; Miller and Slingerland, 2006; Miller et al., 2007; Goren et al., 2014; He et al., 2021; Shi et al., 2021; Zhou et al., 2022a). This model is characterized by a constant tectonic velocity field, where both vertical and horizontal tectonic movement rates vary linearly across a mountain belt. To comprehensively account for the distinct scenarios of tectonic convergence and extension within the mountain belt, two corresponding tectonic-geometric models are established (Fig. 1B&D).

To consistent with previous studies (He et al., 2021; Shi et al., 2021), the horizontal tectonic movement velocities at the edges of the mountain belt are specifically designated as V_p (for the positive side) and V_r (for the negative side). Correspondingly, the uplift rates at the edges of the mountain belt are denoted as U_p and U_r . The width of the mountain belt is denoted as M , with the widths on either side of the MDD specified as D_p and D_r , such that $M = D_p + D_r$. As established in previous studies (Montgomery and Dietrich, 1992; Tucker and Bras, 1998; Duvall, 2004; Braun, 2018), a complete drainage basin system consists of river channels and hillslopes. In this model, the horizontal projections of the main stem river channel lengths on both sides of the MDD are designated as x_p and x_r (Fig. 1A). The cross-sectional widths of these river channels, measured perpendicular to the MDD, are denoted as x_p' and x_r' , while the cross-sectional widths of the hillslopes adjacent to the MDD are represented by $x_{c(p)'}'$ and $x_{c(r)'}'$. This gives the relationships: $D_p = x_p' + x_{c(p)'}'$

99 and $D_r = x_r' + x_{c(r)'}'$ (Fig. 1C).

100 We assume that the mountain belt reaches a topographic steady state, where
101 erosion equals rock uplift, leading to a stable topography (Willett and Brandon, 2002).
102 Notably, in the presence of horizontal tectonic movements, rocks within the mountain
103 belt migrate directionally from the positive to the negative side (Hoskins et al., 2023).
104 In this scenario, although the position of the MDD remains stationary within the fixed
105 spatial coordinate system, it exhibits a counter migration relative to the moving rock
106 mass. This compensatory movement of the MDD occurs in the opposite direction to
107 rock migration, offsetting the displacement rate of the rocks.

108 Detachment limited incision into bedrock is commonly represented using a
109 power-law relationship that incorporates drainage area and channel gradient (Howard
110 and Kerby, 1983; Howard et al., 1994). Building on prior researches (Miller et al.,
111 2007; Goren et al., 2014), the constraint equation for channel profile evolution under
112 the combined effects of vertical uplift (U) and horizontal tectonic movement (V) can
113 be formulated as follows:

$$114 \quad \frac{dz}{dt} = U(x, t) + V(x, t) \frac{dz}{dx} - K(x, t)A(x, t)^m \left(\frac{dz}{dx}\right)^n \quad (1)$$

115 In the above equation, z represents elevation, t represents time, x is the horizontal
116 distance along the channel, and A is the upstream drainage area. The erosion
117 coefficient, K , is a parameter influenced by multiple factors, most notably rock
118 erodibility and precipitation rate. Meanwhile, m and n are the area and slope
119 exponents as defined in previous works (Kirby and Whipple, 2001; Willett et al.,
120 2014). Under steady-state conditions ($dz/dt = 0$) and assuming $n = 1$ within the

121 mountain belt, Eq. 1 can be analytically solved to determine the channel slope as
 122 demonstrated in prior studies (Miller et al., 2007; Kirby and Whipple, 2001; Goren et
 123 al., 2014b):

$$124 \quad \frac{dz}{dx} = \frac{U(x)}{K(x)A(x)^m - V(x)} \quad (2)$$

125 We define the tortuosity coefficient (T) as the ratio of the horizontal distance
 126 along the channel segment (dx) to the horizontal distance measured perpendicular to
 127 the drainage divide (dx') for each individual channel segment, i.e., $T = dx/dx'$.
 128 Assuming T remains constant during the horizontal tectonic movement, the horizontal
 129 movement velocity can be reformulated as $V(x) = T(x') \cdot V(x')$.

130 According to Hack's law, which has been extensively validated in numerous
 131 studies (Hack, 1957; Rigon et al., 1996; Willemín, 2000; Dodds and Rothman, 2000),
 132 the upstream drainage area (A) can be empirically modeled as a function of horizontal
 133 distance. Specifically, $A(x') = k[T(x')(D - x')]^b$, where k and b represent Hack's
 134 coefficient and exponent, respectively. These parameters are closely associated with
 135 the morphometric characteristics of the drainage basin as documented in previous
 136 researches (Walcott and Summerfield, 2009; Shen et al., 2017; Sassolas-Serrayet et
 137 al., 2018). By substituting the aforementioned expressions into Eq. 2, it can be
 138 rewritten as:

$$139 \quad \frac{dz}{T(x') \cdot dx'} = \frac{U(x')}{K(x')T(x')^m k^m (D - x')^{bm} - T(x')V(x')} \quad (3)$$

140 The river longitudinal elevation (z) profile can be expressed by integration from
 141 a base point (x'_b) to an observation point (x'). By incorporating Eq. 3, we obtain the
 142 following expression:

143
$$z(x'_r) - z(x'_p) = \int_{x'_p}^{x'_r} \frac{U(x')}{K(x')T(x')^{bm-1}k^m(D-x')^{bm-V(x')}} dx' \quad (4)$$

144 We assume that the exponents n and b remain constant within the mountain belt,
 145 and the erosion coefficient (K) and tortuosity coefficient (T) are homogeneous on
 146 either side of the MDD as supported by previous researches (Kirby and Whipple,
 147 2001; He et al., 2021; Shi et al., 2021; Zhou et al., 2022a). According to the geometric
 148 relationship of the vertical uplift (U) and horizontal tectonic movement (V) within the
 149 mountain belt, the ratio of the fluvial channel heights on the two sides of the MDD
 150 (H_r/H_p) can be formulated as a ratio of definite integrals in Eq. 4:

151
$$\frac{H_r}{H_p} = \frac{\int_0^{D_r-x'_c(r)} \frac{U_r + \frac{x'_r}{M}(U_p - U_r)}{K_r T_r^{bm-1} k_r^m (D_r - x'_r)^{bm} - V_r - \frac{x'_r}{M}(V_p - V_r)} dx'_r}{\int_0^{D_p-x'_c(p)} \frac{U_p - \frac{x'_p}{M}(U_p - U_r)}{K_p T_p^{bm-1} k_p^m (D_p - x'_p)^{bm} + V_p - \frac{x'_p}{M}(V_p - V_r)} dx'_p} \quad (5)$$

152 Eq. 5 serves as the constraint equation governing the position of the steady-state
 153 MDD within a mountain belt. An analytical solution to this equation exists for $bm = 1$,
 154 whose derivation is detailed in the supplementary materials. For $bm \neq 1$, numerical
 155 methods are required to solve the equation. To intuitively illustrate the relationships
 156 between the MDD's position and its controlling factors, we have developed an
 157 interactive program for the numerical solution of Eq. 5 ([https://github.com/Zhou-](https://github.com/Zhou-Chao0630/SDD-V)
 158 [Chao0630/SDD-V](https://github.com/Zhou-Chao0630/SDD-V)) (Fig. S1).

159 The curves of the MDD position under different controlling factors are illustrated
 160 in Figure 2. The interactive program can plot the curves with different parameters. The
 161 vertical axis of the plots denotes the relative, normalized position of the MDD (D_r/M)
 162 within the mountain belt. Specifically, 0% and 100% mark the positions of negative and
 163 positive boundaries of mountain belts, which are represented by subscripts r and p ,

164 respectively. The horizontal axis of the curves uses the combined form of uplift rate
165 ratio U_r/U_p and U_p/U_r . The dashed line at the center of the graph corresponds to the
166 scenario of uniform uplift (i.e., $U_p = U_r$). The regions to the left and right of the dashed
167 line depict the cases of tilted uplift: the left dips towards the negative side ($U_p > U_r$) and
168 the right towards the positive side ($U_p < U_r$).

169 The steady-state position of MDD is profoundly influenced by the uplift ratio (Fig.
170 2A). If the mountain belt experiences uniform uplift and there is no horizontal
171 movement ($V_p = V_r = 0$), the MDD stabilizes at the midpoint of the mountain belt (D_r/M
172 = 50%). However, with tilted uplift ($U_p \neq U_r$), the MDD position shifts towards the
173 region with a higher uplift rate. Notably, when the uplift rate at one edge of the mountain
174 belt diminishes to zero ($U_r = 0$ or $U_p = 0$), the dimensionless position (D_r/M) of the
175 MDD reaches its maximum deviation (approximately 74% or 26%, respectively). These
176 two extreme positions exhibit mirror symmetry about the central axis of the mountain
177 belt, highlighting the symmetrical nature of the system's response to asymmetric uplift
178 conditions.

179 Horizontal tectonic movement also significantly impacts the MDD position. It
180 causes the displacement of rocks from the positive to the negative side of the mountain
181 belt, thereby driving the MDD to move towards the negative side. For a uniform uplift
182 within the mountain belt ($U_p = U_r$) and a constant horizontal tectonic movement rate
183 ($V_p = V_r = 2$ mm/yr), the dimensionless position of the MDD (D_r/M) is approximately
184 21% (Fig. 2A). This is a notable deviation from the midpoint, exhibiting a significant
185 movement towards the negative edge of the mountain belt. When the horizontal velocity

186 field has a gradient, i.e., decreasing from 2 mm/yr to 1 mm/yr from the positive (V_p) to
187 the negative edge (V_r) due to internal strains, the MDD stabilizes at around 33% (Fig.
188 2B). Compared to the position of 21% under uniform movement (Fig. 2A), the reduced
189 deviation from the midpoint indicates that the internal deformation within the mountain
190 belts mitigates the displacement effect on the MDD's position.

191 Parameters such as river channel height (H), erosion coefficient (K), mountain belt
192 width (M), and hillslope length (x_c') also influence the MDD position (Fig. 2C). An
193 inverse relationship exists between the ratio of river channel heights (H_p/H_r) and the
194 normalized MDD position (D_r/M), indicating that the steady-state MDD shifts towards
195 the side with a higher base level. Erosion coefficient (K) and mountain width (M) are
196 both positively correlated with the normalized MDD position (D_r/M) (Fig. 2D&E).
197 Hence, greater erosion resistance of rocks, less precipitation, or a narrower mountain
198 belt amplify the impact of horizontal tectonic movement on topography. On the effect
199 of hillslope length (x_c') (Fig. 2F), when x_c' increases from 200 m to 800 m, the MDD
200 position changes by approximately 7%. This underscores the significant role played by
201 the proportion of the hillslope and river channel within the drainage basins in
202 determining the steady-state MDD position.

203

204 **3. Numerical simulations**

205 We adopt numerical simulation to verify the constraint equation's reliability. The
206 numerical simulations were conducted using the TopoToolbox Landscape Evolution

207 Model (Campforts et al., 2017), a well-established computational framework for
208 simulating geomorphological processes. Each simulation was started within a
209 rectangular domain with dimensions of 100×200 km² (the mountain belt width, $M =$
210 100 km). The models were initialized with a randomly generated surface,
211 characterized by elevations ranging from 0 to 1 km. To ensure the attainment of a
212 steady-state condition, the simulations were run for a duration exceeding 50 million
213 years (Myr), with a temporal resolution of 0.2 Myr. The simulation parameters were
214 carefully selected to reflect realistic geomorphological conditions. Specifically, the
215 area exponent $m = 0.45$, the slope exponent $n = 1$, the erosional coefficient $K =$
216 6×10^{-6} /yr, the hillslope diffusivity $D_h = 0.03$ m²/yr, and the drainage area threshold A_c
217 $= 0.5$ km². These parameter values were predominantly derived from an extensive
218 review of previous research studies (Willett et al., 2014; He et al., 2021; Shi et al.,
219 2021; Zhou et al., 2022a).

220 We conduct three sets of simulations in which the uniform horizontal tectonic
221 movement velocities (V) are set to 0, 1, and 2 mm/yr, respectively. For each set, the
222 uplift patterns are systematically varied. Initially, the uplift rate on the positive side is
223 fixed at $U_p = 1$ mm/yr, while the uplift rate on the negative side (U_r) is adjusted to
224 range from 0 to 1 mm/yr at an increment of 0.2 mm/yr. Thus, the U_r/U_p ratio varies
225 from 0 to 1. Subsequently, with U_r fixed at 1 mm/yr, U_p is changed from 0 to 1 mm/yr
226 in 0.2 mm/yr steps, so the U_p/U_r ratio ranges from 0 to 1. In total, we create 33
227 numerical models, 11 per set. The results of nine specific models, namely those with
228 $U_p/U_r = 0$, $U_p/U_r = 1$, and $U_r/U_p = 0$, are shown in Figure 3; the rest are detailed in the

229 Supplementary materials (Fig. S2). For each numerical model, the maximum,
230 minimum, and average MDD positions (D_r/M) are measured and plotted on the
231 corresponding parameter curve (Fig. 3J), allowing direct comparison between
232 numerical simulation results and the curves derived from the constraint equation.

233 The numerical simulation results generally agree with the curves predicted by the
234 constraint equation (Fig. 3J). For different uplift patterns under the same horizontal
235 tectonic movement rate (Fig. 3A, B&C, as examples), as the ratio of uplift rates
236 changes from $U_p/U_r = 0$ to 1 and then reverses to $U_r/U_p = 0$, the normalized MDD
237 position (D_r/M) continuously shifts towards the negative side. This supports the
238 conclusion that MDD always migrates towards the side with a higher uplift rate to
239 attain equilibrium. Moreover, comparing different horizontal tectonic movement
240 under the same uplift pattern (Fig. 3A, D&G, as examples), as the horizontal tectonic
241 movement rates (V) increase from 0, 1 to 2 mm/yr, the MDD position (D_r/M)
242 progressively moves to the negative side, which is consistent with the constraint
243 equation's predictions. In all simulations, the position of the steady-state MDD (D_r/M)
244 closely matches the predicted values, and the overall variation pattern conforms to the
245 equation's expectations (Fig. 3J). This further confirms the reliability of the constraint
246 equation.

247

248 **4. Application to natural cases**

249 We apply the constraint equation to the Wutai Shan, a rift shoulder during the

250 Cenozoic extension in North China, and the Min Shan, a mountain range located in
251 the eastern margin of the Tibetan Plateau (Fig. 4A).

252 The Wutai Shan is primarily composed of metamorphic and igneous rocks
253 (Clinkscales et al., 2020). The region has a semi-arid climate with annual precipitation
254 between 400 and 600 mm. No significant precipitation variation occurs across the
255 MDDs (<http://worldclim.org>). The tilted uplift of Wutai Shan is governed by the
256 Wutai Shan Fault on its northwestern boundary, which is comparable with the
257 kinematic model in Fig. 1D. The Quaternary throw rate of the Wutai Shan Fault is ca.
258 0.8~1.6 mm/yr (Middleton et al., 2017) and Late-Cenozoic throw rate is ca. 0.25
259 mm/yr (Clinkscales et al., 2020). We adopt an uplift rate of 0.50 mm/yr for the
260 northwestern margin, following Zhou et al. (2024), and assume zero uplift for the
261 southeastern margin due to a near-zero channel steep index ($U_p = 0.5$ mm/yr, $U_r = 0$
262 mm/yr). Assuming no internal extension within the Wutai Shan and a fault dip of 70° ,
263 the horizontal tectonic movement rates (V_p & V_r) are calculated as 0.18 mm/yr. Zhou
264 et al. (2022a) estimated the stable position of Wutai Shan's MDD without considering
265 horizontal tectonic movement. By applying the new equation and using the same
266 channels and parameters, we find a stable MDD position at $D_r/M = 60\%$ (Fig. 4A&B;
267 Table 1). This is approximately 7% lower than the previous estimate of 67% (Zhou et
268 al., 2022a). This discrepancy highlights the significant impact of horizontal tectonic
269 movement. According to Zhou et al. (2024), the MDD is currently migrating
270 northward at 0.21–0.27 mm/yr relative to the bedrock. Our analysis suggests that the
271 migration rate will decrease to 0.18 mm/yr after migrating 8 km northward to the 60%

272 position. Such a migration rate is equal to the horizontal movement rate, but in
273 opposite directions. By then, the MDD of Wutai Shan will reach equilibrium (if all
274 conditions remain).

275 The Min Shan is bounded on the east by the Huya Fault, and on the west by the
276 Minjiang Fault (Fig. 4C). Thrusting along the Huya Fault controls the west-dipping
277 uplift pattern of the Min Shan (Tan et al., 2019), which is comparable with the
278 kinematic model in Fig. 1B. Regional lithology consists primarily of Paleozoic–
279 Mesozoic platformal, shallow-water siliciclastic rocks and reef-bearing limestones,
280 intruded by the Triassic granitoids (Burchfiel et al., 1995). The bedrock's erosion
281 coefficient (K) is estimated at $\sim 1.52 \times 10^{-6} \text{ m}^{0.1} \text{ yr}^{-1}$ (Zhou et al., 2022b). Mean annual
282 precipitation ranges from 600 to 800 mm, with minimal spatial variation across the
283 main drainage divide (MDD) (<http://worldclim.org>). We analyze a river pair across
284 Min Shan's MDD to estimate its stable position (Fig. 4C). River parameters are listed
285 in Table 1 and supplementary materials. Assuming the Huya Fault dip at $55 \pm 15^\circ$,
286 using a vertical slip rate of 0.3 mm/yr for the Huya Fault (Li et al., 2006; Tan et al.,
287 2019), we derive the horizontal tectonic rates (V_p & V_r) of ~ 0.21 mm/yr (0.11-0.35
288 mm/yr). Thermal history from low-temperature thermochronology (Tan et al., 2019)
289 supports an uplift ratio (U_p/U_r) of 0.5. Application of the new equation locates the
290 stable MDD at $D_r/M = 72\%$ (Fig. 4C&D), closely matching its present position at
291 $\sim 74\%$, indicating relative stability in a spatial reference frame. This result is
292 reinforced by the correspondence between the MDD's westward migration rate (Zhou
293 et al., 2022b) and the equivalent eastward horizontal tectonic rate.

294

295 **Table 1.** Parameters for determining the stable position of MDD for the two natural
296 examples. The parameters $m = 0.45$ and $n = 1$ are adopted in the calculation. The river
297 channel parameters of the Wutai Shan is from Zhou et al. (2022b), and those of the
298 Min Shan are shown in Supplementary materials (Figs. S3&S4).

Example	H_p/H_r	M (km)	K ($\text{m}^{0.1}\text{yr}^{-1}$)	b	$x'_{c(p)}$ (km)	$x'_{c(r)}$ (km)	T_p	T_r	k_p	k_r
Wutai Shan	1.11	46.03	6.25×10^{-6}	1.4	0.8	0.2	1.44	1.27	198 $\text{m}^{0.6}$	136 $\text{m}^{0.6}$
Min Shan	0.55	43.00	1.52×10^{-6}	1.3	1.0	1.8	1.38	1.46	299 $\text{m}^{0.7}$	642 $\text{m}^{0.7}$

299

300 5. Discussion

301 5.1 Advantages of the new equation

302 Understanding the mechanisms that shape mountain landscape is essential in
303 Earth system science. Willett et al. (2001, 2002) pioneered this field by employing
304 numerical simulations to examine how various parameters influence mountain belt
305 morphologies. Specifically, they introduced the concept of topographic steady state in
306 mountain belts and systematically analyzed diverse morphological expressions. Their
307 work investigated the impacts of multiple parameters, including horizontal/vertical
308 tectonic movements, fluvial erosion, and hillslope denudation, with findings
309 supported by natural field examples. Subsequently, Miller et al. (2006, 2007) and
310 Goren et al. (2014) advanced analytical solutions for determining MDD positions. In
311 particular, Miller et al. (2006, 2007) developed an analytical solution for river slopes

312 in mountain belts, considering the combined effects of tectonic uplift and horizontal
313 movement. Goren et al. (2014) further derived an equation for MDD position that
314 considers the effects of spatial variations in tectonic uplift, horizontal tectonic
315 movement, and the orographic precipitation.

316 Building on these foundational efforts, He et al. (2021), Shi et al. (2021), and
317 Zhou et al. (2022a) have refined the constraint equations for MDD positions.
318 Specifically, He et al. (2021) derived formulas for the steady-state MDD position
319 under individual conditions of tectonic uplift and horizontal movement, respectively,
320 in which the uplift rate of mountain belts varies along a spatial gradient. This progress
321 has enabled better quantification of tectonic impact on MDD positions. Following
322 that, Shi et al. (2021) found that when uplift rate varies linearly across the mountain,
323 the uplift rate ratio determines MDD positions. Zhou et al. (2022a) further expanded
324 this work by quantifying the effects of non-tectonic factors, such as lithology,
325 precipitation, base-level elevation, and drainage basin morphology, on the stable
326 position of MDD.

327 Previous studies have largely examined the controlling factors separately,
328 limiting the general applicability of the constraint equations across diverse and
329 complex conditions in nature. Our study addresses this gap by fully integrating
330 tectonic uplift, horizontal movement, and non-tectonic elements to establish a
331 comprehensive constraint equation for the steady-state MDD position. This approach
332 allows for broader, more generalized geological analysis and provides a more robust
333 tool for understanding tectonics and surface process interactions in mountainous

334 regions.

335

336 **5.2 Limitations**

337 This study uses a simplified geometric model, assuming that the vertical and
338 horizontal tectonic movement rates vary linearly across the mountain belt but remain
339 constant over time. However, natural conditions often deviate from these assumptions
340 due to complex faulting, folding, and temporal changes in tectonic activity. Even in
341 relatively simple tectonic extension settings (Fig. 1D)—where a block is bounded by
342 a single fault—the uplift pattern may depart from linearity (King and Ellis, 1990; Ellis
343 et al., 1999; Goren et al., 2014). In addition, the temporal variations in tectonic
344 movements that occur throughout the complex evolutionary processes of mountain
345 belts have made the situation even more complex. Understanding the spatiotemporal
346 variations of tectonic movements remains a key challenge. With adequate data, it
347 would be feasible to construct tailored geometric models based on the simplified
348 model presented herein, and generate more accurate results.

349 The surface process model employed in this study is grounded in the theory of
350 detachment-limited channels (Howard and Kerby, 1983; Howard et al., 1994). This
351 model applies to bedrock channel incision in non-sedimentary environments. Notably,
352 this theory depends on multiple empirical parameters. For instance, Hack's Law, an
353 empirical relationship between upstream drainage area and horizontal distance along
354 channels, involves a coefficient (k) and an exponent (b) derived solely from regression
355 analysis of actual data. Errors in regression analysis will be inherited in the

356 calculation results of the constraint equation. Furthermore, in practical applications,
357 some parameters used in the constraint equation may vary significantly. For example,
358 the slope exponent (n) may range from 0.6 to 4 (Kirby and Whipple, 2001; Lague,
359 2014), while concavity (m/n) can vary between 0.4 and 0.6 (Gailleton et al., 2021) in
360 natural settings. Accurate measurement of these parameters is therefore critical to
361 ensuring the precision of results derived from the constraint equation. Overcoming
362 these challenges remains complex.

363

364 **5. Conclusions**

365 The steady-state main drainage divide (MDD) shifts toward regions with a
366 higher uplift rate, higher base level, greater rock erosion resistance, and lower
367 precipitation. Additionally, it migrates in the direction of horizontal tectonic
368 movement, with migration degree influenced by mountain belt width and hillslope
369 process proportion.

370 The Wutai Shan MDD will migrate northward ~8 km to reach its stable position.
371 At that point, its northward bedrock-relative migration rate will decrease from the
372 current 0.21–0.27 mm/yr to ~0.18 mm/yr, matching the horizontal tectonic movement
373 rate in magnitude but opposite in direction. In contrast, the Min Shan MDD is close to
374 its steady-state position, corroborated by the near equivalence of its westward
375 bedrock-relative migration rate and eastward horizontal tectonic movement rate.

376 Although the current equation still includes mathematical simplifications, it is

377 the most comprehensive MDD position constraint equation to date. This study's
378 numerical simulation results further validate its reliability. To enhance its practical
379 utility, we developed an interactive program ([https://github.com/Zhou-
380 Chao0630/SDD-V](https://github.com/Zhou-Chao0630/SDD-V)) to facilitate its use in specific natural cases.

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385 **Data and materials availability**

386 The numerical simulations were conducted using the TopoToolbox Landscape
387 Evolution Model. The program used to generate the curves of the steady-state
388 positions of the MDD is available on <https://github.com/Zhou-Chao0630/SDD-V>.

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530

531 **Figures and captions**

532

533 **Figure 1.** Schematic diagrams showing the parameters applied in this study. (A) The
 534 top-view of the surface morphology in a mountain belt. The black dashed line represents
 535 the MDD, and the blue lines represent the drainage systems on both sides of the MDD.
 536 (B) The cross-section view of a mountain belt. The black dashed line represents the
 537 MDD, and the black solid lines represent the longitudinal profiles of the two channels
 538 on both sides of the MDD. (C-D) Kinematic models for tectonic convergence and
 539 extension. The black dashed lines with arrows denote the tectonic movement, whereas
 540 the red lines represent the active faults. The blue arrows represent the horizontal
 541 movement. Subscripts r and p denote the negative and positive side of mountain belts,
 542 respectively. Revised from He et al. (2021) and Zhou et al. (2022a).

543

544

545 **Figure 2.** The stable position of MDD under different parameters of different factors.

546 The vertical axis is the dimensionless position of the MDD within the mountain belt

547 (Dr/M), and the horizontal axis is uplift rate ratio (U_r/U_p or U_p/U_r). The dashed line at

548 the center of the graph corresponds to the scenario of uniform uplift (i.e., $U_p = U_r$). The

549 stable position of MDD under (A) constant horizontal tectonic movement ($V_p = V_r$), (B)

550 gradient horizontal tectonic movement ($V_p \neq V_r$), (C) different river channel height (H),

551 (D) different erosion coefficient (K), (E) different mountain belt width (M), and (F)

552 different hillslope length (x_c'). Other parameters including $m = 0.45$, $n = 1$, $b = 1.2$, $T =$

553 1.2 and $k = 400 \text{ m}^{0.8}$.

554

555

556 **Figure 3.** Comparison between numerical simulation results and formula predictions.

557 **(A-I)** The numerical simulations at different conditions. The black curves represent the

558 steady-state position of the MDD. **(J)** Comparison between the curves plotted by the

559 constraint equation and MDD positions from numerical simulations. The symbols and

560 short lines above/below denote the mean, maximum, and minimum values of MDD

561 positions from numerical simulations. The black, red, and blue symbols and curves
 562 represent numerical simulation results and corresponding curves under $V_p = V_r = 0$
 563 mm/yr, $V_p = V_r = 1$ mm/yr, and $V_p = V_r = 2$ mm/yr, respectively. The hollow and solid
 564 symbols denote the simulation results shown in this figure and the Supplementary
 565 materials (Fig. S2), respectively. The details are shown in Supplementary materials
 566 (Table S1).
 567

568
 569 **Figure 4.** Prediction of the MDD's stable position for the natural examples.
 570 Topographic map of (A) the Wutai Shan in North China and (C) the Min Shan in
 571 eastern margin of the Tibetan Plateau. Theoretical stable positions (green) and present
 572 positions (orange) of the MDDs for (B) the Wutai Shan and (D) the Min Shan. The

573 dashed line indicates results from previous studies that did not account for horizontal

574 tectonic movements, whereas the solid line represents the outcomes integrating this

575 factor derived from the constraint equation in this study.

576